

Glossary for the Learning Objectives Matrix on the Topic of Research Data Management (RDM)

V3

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Glossary of the Learning Objectives Matrix for RDM

This glossary provides explanations of terms in the context of the Learning Objectives Matrix for Research Data Management (LOM-RDM).

The definitions listed correspond with the content and objectives of the matrix and serve to create a common level of understanding for the use and interpretation of

the learning objectives. A conscious decision was made not to formulate definitions with the goal of being commonly applicable or comprehensive. Instead, the terms are related to the matrix and the topics covered therein. Individual terms might need to be defined more broadly or differently in other contexts.

The glossary is therefore intended as a work-related guide and not as a universally applicable reference.

Access control

Access control is a security technology based on physical and logical authorization and authentication components. It ensures that users can only access resources and perform actions for which they are authorized. (cf. Wikipedia, n.d.-e)

Anonymization

Anonymization is the totality of measures to erase any personal references in the data so that the individual details about personal or factual circumstances can no longer be assigned to a specific or identifiable natural person or only with a disproportionate amount of time, cost and workforce.

Archiving

Archiving is the secure storage of deliberately selected research data, including its metadata and other documentation, for a defined retention period. The aim is to keep them accessible beyond the end of the project, to enable their subsequent use, to guarantee their integrity and to demonstrate compliance with good scientific practice. (cf. Affective Societies, n.d.)

Authenticity

In the context of digital long-term archiving, authenticity is a quality feature of data. Data is authentic if it is genuine, verifiable, and trustworthy. (Porath, 2020, p. 30)

Authority control

Standard data are structured data sets created by authorized institutions to identify entities such as persons, organizations, places, subjects or works uniquely and consistently.

Competency

‘Competency describes (...) the ability and willingness of the individual to use knowledge and skills as well as personal, social and methodological abilities and to behave in a thoughtful and individually and socially responsible manner.’ (Bundesländer-Koordinierungsstelle für den Deutschen Qualifikationsrahmen für lebenslanges Lernen, 2013, p. 4)

Conceptual system

‘A conceptual system is a system of clearly distinguishable terms (also concepts, classes, objects, elements) that are connected to each other by various relationships (e.g. hierarchical/holistic).’ (cf. Wikipedia, n.d.-a)

Controlled vocabulary

A controlled vocabulary is a collection of terms in a specific context that is created according to defined rules to ensure unambiguity. Controlled vocabularies range from simple word lists such as standardized data to more complex structured vocabularies such as taxonomies, classifications and thesauri. (cf. Spree, n.d.-a)

Data

Data are (analog or digital) objects and signs, for example images, measurement results, or words, which can be the basis for obtaining information in any conceivable form. Data can be structured or unstructured. (cf. Persike, 2023)

Data cleansing

Data cleansing is the process of removing or correcting incorrect (originally incorrect or outdated), redundant, inconsistent, or incorrectly formatted data in order to improve data quality. (cf. Wikipedia, n.d.-b)

Data curation

Data curation is a managed process throughout the data lifecycle, by which data/data collections are cleansed, documented, standardized, formatted and inter-related. This includes versioning data, or forming a new collection from several data sources, annotating with metadata, adding codes to raw data. (cf. CODATA RDM Terminology Working Group, 2023)

Data format

'Data format is a term from data processing that defines how data is structured and presented', for example a tabular time series of a temperature measurement. (cf. Wikipedia, n.d.-c)

Data protection

Data protection is a set of measures for the legal and ethical protection of personal data against unauthorized processing and misuse.

Data quality

Data quality is a measure of the condition of data. It refers to quantitative characteristics and properties such as accuracy and completeness as well as qualitative aspects such as relevance or comprehensibility. The aim is to ensure that research data is reliable, consistent, precise and useful in order to achieve valid scientific results. There is no absolute quality standard, as the quality of data always depends on the specific application. (cf. Stedman, n.d.)

Data security

Data security means protecting digital data, such as those in a database, from destructive forces and from the unwanted actions of unauthorized users, such as a cyberattack or a data breach. (cf. Data security, n.d.)

Data steward

Data stewards are individuals or roles that support researchers in the creation, management, quality assurance, protection and sustainable use of research data, providing also training and advice. A distinction is made between central data stewards, who work for the entire institution, and decentralized or embedded data stewards, who work on a discipline-specific basis at faculty, institute, or project level. The role of data stewards varies in different areas and may overlap with other roles. (cf. forschungsdaten.info, n. d.-a; cf. The Turing Way Community, n.d.)

Data type

A data type is a classification of data that defines value ranges for data. Basic data types are, for example, integers (Integer), decimal numbers (Real or Float), character strings (String) or Boolean (true, false). Mixed forms and combinations are also possible. Certain operations are predefined with a data type.

Didactic scenario

A didactic scenario is the planned and structured combination of learning content, learning objectives, learning environments, didactic methods, and media. (cf. Reinmann, 2011, p. 8)

Evaluation

Evaluation is a systematic and empirical review of processes, concepts, projects or measures using defined methods and criteria in order to assess their effectiveness, efficiency, or quality. (cf. Rindermann, 2003)

Feedback

Feedback is subjective feedback to individuals and/or groups regarding their performance or competencies, behaviors, and/or impact (external perception). (cf. Reinhold et al., n.d.)

File format

The file format is the specific technical implementation of a file, i.e., how the data is stored, represented, and interpreted or processed. As a rule, file formats can be recognized by file extensions, for example PNG or TIFF.

File naming convention

A file naming convention is a defined rule for the uniform and comprehensible naming of files. (cf. Biernacka et al., 2023, pp. 50-51)

File type

File type is a categorization of files according to the type of content of the data, for example image, text, video, audio, without referring to the specific technical implementation.

Informed consent

Informed consent is consent to voluntary participation in a research project. It is based on clearly understandable information on responsibilities, the purposes of processing personal data and revocation. The design of informed consent must address ethical and legal requirements. (cf. BfDI, n.d.; see Verordnung, 2016)

Integrity

Integrity is a quality characteristic of data that depends on its completeness and integrity. Integral data is neither intentionally nor unintentionally altered or destroyed by a technical error. (cf. DIN 31644, 2012)

Interoperability

Interoperability is the ability of two or more systems or products to exchange data directly and use it functionally without using conversion processes or adapters. (cf. Holznagel & Freese, 2022)

IT infrastructures

IT infrastructures are all technical and organizational components of software, hardware, networks, and the associated services that make up the IT environment of an institution. (cf. IT Infrastruktur, n.d.)

Learning objective

'A learning objective describes the verifiable increase in knowledge, skills and attitudes in relation to a specific learning content' (Stangl, n.d.), which should be achieved at the end of a learning process. (cf. Gundermann, 2024)

Long-term archiving

Long-term archiving is the permanent storage of (digital) information and the preservation of its technical and content-related usability over exceptionally long, undefined periods of time. This includes not only the storage of data, but also specific measures to ensure the integrity, authenticity, and interpretability of the archived information. (cf. Neuroth et al., 2009)

Metadata

'Metadata is structured data that contains information about other data - data about data.' (Biernacka et al., 2023, p. 59)

Metadata schema

A metadata schema is a collection of metadata elements and properties that can be used to describe and process objects and their relationships to each other in a structured way. (cf. Oellers & Rörtgen, 2024, p. 8)

Metadata standard

A metadata standard is a set of rules that ensures a common understanding of metadata for specific applications or contexts. These agreements include standardized rules for the syntactic and semantic interpretation of data. Metadata standards are published by standardization organizations. (cf. Oellers & Rörtgen, 2024, p. 14)

Object-orientation

Object-orientation is an approach to software development. Complex systems are conceptually defined with the help of objects. Certain attributes (properties) and methods, for example operations, are assigned to these objects. An object does not necessarily have to describe a real object. (cf. Wikipedia, n.d.-d)

Ontology

An ontology is a formal conceptual model that is used to describe and visualize a specific subject area. It contains terms, their properties, and the relationships between these terms. (cf. Rehbein, 2017)

Personal data

Personal data is any information that relates to an identified or identifiable living individual (data subject). Different pieces of information, which together can lead to the identification of a particular person, may also be considered personal data. (European Commission, n.d.)

Programming structure

A programming structure is an essential element of computer programs that determines how a program runs and under which conditions parts of the program are called, skipped, or repeated. Basic programming structures are instructions, repetitions, branches, and subroutines.

Proprietary

Proprietary is a characteristic of products that are completely controlled by the owners and are tied to specific technology. (see proprietary - spelling, definition, meaning, synonyms, examples, n.d.)

Pseudonymization

Pseudonymization is the entirety of measures to change personal data so that it can no longer be assigned to a specific person without the use of additional information. The additional information must be stored separately and under access control. (cf. Verordnung, 2016, p. 4)

RDM services

The term RDM services is an overarching collective term that describes all services and performances in the field of research data management, such as specific RDM tools, consulting, and training.

Repository

A repository is a managed storage location for diverse types of digital objects. It enables open or restricted access to such objects. (cf. forschungsdaten.info, n. d.-b; cf. Kaiser & Rathmann, n. d.)

Taxonomy

A taxonomy is a hierarchically structured, controlled vocabulary that organizes terms into categories or classes according to certain criteria. (cf. Spree, n.d.-b)

Teaching and learning process

The teaching and learning process is the learning goal-oriented interactive process in which knowledge, skills and competences are imparted using didactic methods in a target group-oriented manner. The process includes both the activities on the part of the teacher and the activities on the part of the learner.

Thesaurus

A thesaurus is a hierarchically structured, controlled vocabulary in which synonymous and related terms are placed in relationships. (cf. Zeng, 2008)

Threshold of originality

The threshold of originality or level of originality is a criterion in copyright law that is used to assess whether a work is worthy of protection. It is not a firmly defined legal concept but must be reassessed on the basis of each work. If a work has sufficient originality, individuality, or artistic quality, it is considered to be an independent creation and thus has the level of originality and is subject to copyright protection. In contrast, works that do not have a level of originality are considered to be in the public domain.

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